

**THE IMPACT OF YOG ON THE STUDENTS' INTEREST IN RELATION TO TWO –YEARS
B.Ed. COURSE**

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ABSTRACT

योगेस्थः कुरु कर्माणि सगं व्यक्त्वा धनंजय ।
सिद्धय सिद्धयोः समोभूत्वा समत्वं योग उच्यते ॥

– गीता

In today's fast-paced world, people are chasing after material possessions, sacrificing their peace of mind in the process. Stress, trauma, anxiety, and frustration have become common experiences for many. Consequently, there's a growing recognition of the significance of incorporating yoga education into our lives. The current B.Ed training program has been kept as a two-year program by the National Council for Teacher Education, 2014. This is a commendable work because a teacher builds the society. If he is not fully skilled from the human and professional point of view then it is not possible to build the society. Along with this, due to the increasing competition in the society, teachers are also suffering from many mental diseases. It is necessary to develop Yog education for the complete development of teacher's personality. Therefore, it is necessary to have theoretical and practical aspects of Yog or Yog Darshan in the teacher education curriculum. To give practical form to Yoga philosophy, outgoing Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi has declared June 21 as World Yoga Day through the United Nations. In this, 177 countries of the world have recognized World Yoga Day.

Introduction:

“Yoga and physical education have been given less importance in the school curriculum, whereas for the all-round development of the child, the development of the child and the quality of the school are linked through yoga and physical education.” **-NCTE-.2005**

Through yoga and physical education, the child is freed from physical weaknesses and is provided physical health. (Ganrot, 1976, Ganguly M., 1976) **–NCERT, 2006**

Uttar Pradesh has also compulsorily included Yog and Physical Education in the curriculum of Secondary Education Council from class 9 to 12 from the session 2017-18.

Yog guru Baba Ramdev ji says that - "Yog is the heritage of our ancestors. There should be no politics on it." There is also meditation, when we become Narayan from a human being and Brahm from a living being, then through this a pure character like a yogi develops. The University Grants Commission has directed universities to conduct detailed training on yoga protocol. “The Ministry of Human Resource Development has declared and decided..... 21st June, 2017 as the 3rd International Yog Day.”

Throwing light on the importance of Yog in Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, Honorable, Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi said that - "Yog is like salt in life" "Yog is working to connect the world."

Maharishi Patanjali is the originator of Yog philosophy. That Yog means control of mental tendencies. The main subject of Yog philosophy is the practice of Yog. There are eight parts of yog practice which are known as Ashtanga - Yama Niyama, Asana Pranayam, Pratyahara Dharana, Dhyana and Samadhi. According to Yog, God is the best subject of meditation for concentration of mind and for self-knowledge. According to Yog philosophy, God is considered the Supreme Being. He is above all living beings and is free from defects. Maharishi Patanjali has given prominence to the word Samadhi in the perspective of Yog for attaining God. In which he said, control of mental tendencies is the real yog.

Description of Yog philosophy is presented in abundance in Indian philosophy. But we get its complete information in Patanjali Yog Darshan as well as in the chapters of Upanishads and Geeta. It is said that Lord Krishna had complete knowledge of Mahabharata. Therefore he was named Yogeshwar.

The researcher has selected the research title keeping in mind the entire Indian competition so that a high quality teacher can be created by re-developing the declining dignity and morality of teachers in Indian education.

Under the B.Ed two-year course, the researcher tries to know that on the basis of the changed curriculum, spiritual, moral and character changes is seen among the B.Ed trainees as well as their interest is developed in the B.Ed trainees.

Review of literature:

When any researcher or common man finds any problem, he first tries to find out whether any work related to the related problem has been done in the past or not. If any work (research) has been done related to that problem, then the researcher tries to find out whether any work related to that problem has been done in the past or not. Revisiting the results is called a review of that literature. The format, form and nature of Yog philosophy related to teaching training presented by various researchers are different for the development of modern teachers.

The following researches have been studied by the researcher to review the research literature.

Das K., ‘Concept of personality in Sankhya-Yog and Geeta’ -Ph.D....1975

The main objective of the presented research is to develop all aspects of personality in Sankhya-Yog. All aspects of personality can be developed through Sankhya-Yog. In Sankhya Yog, personality is considered to be a dynamic institution in which the principles of psycho-physical, nature building and self-confidence have been given the form of consciousness. It is through Yog that the physical foundation of the personality is provided.

Dev B.R., ‘Spiritual elements in the education philosophy of Mahatma Gandhi’

Ph.D., M.N.A.M.S.U. 1981

The researcher found in his research that the main objective of all types of education is to analyze oneself which is impossible without sadhana. The researcher tried to find out that both philosophy of life and philosophy of education are necessary for spiritual development.

Shankar, Hari, “Comparative study of philosophical and educational ideas of Maharishi Aurobindo and Rousseau”

Ph.D., (Pedagogy), Kumaon University

In his research, the researcher has also given importance to Yog philosophy under the philosophical and educational ideas of Maharishi Aurobindo and Rousseau. Maharishi Aurobindo considers Sankhya, Vedic values and Yog as important for attaining the supreme human being.

Bhanot, P. and Shankar G., 'Need for integrated yog in education' -Ph.D., (Phy.Edu) CCS. Agri., Uni. Haryana, 1995.

In the following research, researchers have reported the inclusion of yog and physical education in the curriculum and its positive results.

Dr. Singh, Bajrang Dev, (1994) 'Conditioning programme with and without yogic exercise on selected physical and psychological variables'

The researcher has linked Yog with natural development in the following research. In which physical, moral and psychological aspects are included.

Dr. Sandhu, Rakam Singh, (1994) "Effect of selected yog asana on motor abilities of high school student"

The researcher examined what effect the third Yog Asana of Yogsana in Ashtanga Yog has on the fundamental ability of matriculation students, in which the researcher found that regular Yogsana affects the all-round development of the child.

Goswami, Harshvardhan, (Gurukul Kangri University Haridwar) 'Critical classical study of Pranayama in the context of health and physical ability'

The researcher obtained the result from his research that to attain Purushartha Chatushtya, it is necessary for a person to be healthy because a person works hard to earn a living and can enjoy worldly pleasures with the money earned. One can attain salvation by performing auspicious deeds.

Need and Importance of the Study:

In the Bhagavad Gita, Lord Shri Krishna, while explaining the importance of yog to Arjuna, has said-

योगी सुंजीत सतवात्मानं रहसि स्थितः ।
एकाकी यताचितात्मा निरापीर परिग्रहः ॥ (10,ध्यानयोग)

That is, a yogi should always remain in a secluded place with his body, mind and soul engaged in God and should control his mind very carefully. The only objective of this exploratory method of the researcher is that only through Yog philosophy, moral values and interest can be developed in the B.Ed

trainees. Maharishi Patanjali has considered Yog as the path to attain God in Yog Sutra. Dr. Radhakrishnan - 'The aim of Yog philosophy is not to propound spiritual theory but to indicate in a practical way how salvation can be achieved through an ascetic life.

Maharishi Vyas, the commentator of Patanjali's Yog Sutra, has said about the epistemology of Yog philosophy that - The student, through the excellent desire of the practice of religious scriptures, inference and contemplation, advances insight through these three methods and attains the highest success in life.

Title of the Research Study:

The title of the present study is as follows- **“THE IMPACT OF YOG ON THE STUDENTS’ INTEREST IN RELATION TO TWO –YEARS B.Ed. COURSE”**

Objectives of the study:

The researcher has given the following objectives related to the present research:

- 1.To see quality improvement in teacher education curriculum through yog.
- 2.To see the relation in between Yog and interest among B.Ed. trainee.
- 3.To awaken interest in yog among trainee teachers.

Hypotheses of the study:

The following hypotheses and assumptions have been developed for the present research study.

1. Yog is helpful in the quality improvement in teacher education programme.
2. B.Ed trainees have interest in yog.
3. There is no interest takes place among the trainee teachers through Yog.

Alternative Hypothesis:

1. An interest takes place among the trainee teachers through Yog.

Research Methodology:

Descriptive survey method has been used in the present research study. The main characteristic of the survey method is to systematically collect data from the population or sample through study forms or questionnaires. Questionnaire was made available to different groups of the sample, after which data related to them were collected.

The present study aimed to understand the interest of B. Ed students in the yog teaching and gather their insights on improving it. The study involved 200 B. Ed Two years’ students from

Bulandshahr district, Uttar Pradesh. Using a custom questionnaire, the researcher collected data and uncovered several key findings.

Students participating in the study emphasized the need for various stakeholders to create new policies promoting and making yog more accessible to the students. They advocated for the recruitment of more yog courses as a necessary step. Furthermore, they highlighted the potential of yog education in fostering not just personal but also societal harmony and development.

In the present research study, the method of research study is descriptive survey to arouse interest and usefulness of B.Ed trainees towards yog because descriptive survey aims to describe and analyze what. In this method, to obtain information about certain facts, appropriate tools are selected and developed to meet the objectives.

Sample and Sampling:

Keeping in mind all the circumstances related to the present research study, the researcher concludes that the B.Ed trainees studying in B.Ed colleges of Bulandshahr district have been selected by random sampling method. The present research is focused on 200 students-teachers.

The present research method presents complete representation and significance of the students selected through random square method of the population. In this, the population has been classified on the basis of criteria, by doing this the difficulty level of research can be reduced. And after selecting all the units, they can be easily included.

Variables of the study:

In the current study the following variable are measured:

I. Independent Variable-

- Yog

II. Dependent Variables-

- Students interest
- Two years B.Ed. Curriculum students

Selection of Tool:

To measure the educational variables in the research study, the researcher used a self-made questionnaire based on interest of B.Ed trainees towards yog. This questionnaire has been based on Likerts five point scale.

Selection and Administration of Data:

After the construction of the tool researcher makes strategic plan to collect the data, firstly researcher makes a list of all the colleges which would be feasible to selection of the sample and collection of the data. Then researcher select 05 institutions from Bulandshahr district from the total colleges comprise the target population. This selection of colleges based on the convenience and transportation facilities and area covered by sample. After that researcher contacted to the principles/heads of the selected colleges and requested for data collection. All of the principles gave permission. Before collection of the data researcher makes the list of B.Ed. students in order to collect the data randomly. Necessary scoring process was included in the research work, after collecting the facts from the self-made questionnaires.

Statistical Methods:

Mean, SD and T-test has been used to fulfill the research objectives of the present study. The Hypotheses were assessed at 0.01 & 0.05 significance levels. The interpretation was entirely guided by the study's objectives and hypotheses.

The current research aimed to examine the impact of yog on the interest of students studying in two years B.Ed. course. Yog was considered the independent variable, while interest and B.Ed. two years course were regarded as dependent variables.

To start, descriptive statistical methods were applied to the data, specifically calculating the mean standard deviation and t-test for both variables. The findings are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Showing the detailed description of the Variables

Showing the detailed impact of Yog					
Yog	Number	Mean	SD	t-value	Significance level (.01 &.05)
B.Ed.		31.12	3.21		

Two year course Students	200			3.86	.01 Significance level
Interest		29.14	3.99		

Findings and Discussion:

In the present study the first objective of the study is to see the quality improvement in teacher education curriculum through yog. This study was initiated due to the concerning prevalence of interest among a significant portion of B.Ed. two years course students. The second objective of the study is to examine the relation in between Yog and interest among B.Ed. trainee. The results indicate that the yog and interest are significantly correlated among the students of B.Ed. two years course. The third objective of the study is to find awaken interest in yog among trainee teachers. This problem often leads to increased concentration levels and interest of students.

The study's findings, particularly through the t-ratio analysis, highlighted a notable positive effect of engaging in yog practice on both B.Ed. Two years course students and Interest. Moreover, the results indicated a significant and encouraging correlation between yog and the interest of Two years B.Ed. Course students.

Delimitations of the study:

After determining the present research study problem and research objective the study was delimited since the scope of the problem is very broad and detailed. Therefore, its study is not possible in limited period of time, resources and facilities. Keeping in mind the time resources and facilities, the scope of study is limited to 05 teaching-training colleges of Bulandshahr district of Uttar Pradesh state. In this research work, 200 B.Ed trainees have been selected as sample.

Educational Implications:

In this study, the researcher has tried to prove the significance of the impact of Yog on the trainees studying in B.Ed. educational institutions. In which, based on the results obtained from the study, the researcher found that keeping in mind the future life of the trainee teachers through yog education, it would be beneficial for the trainees to prove themselves by solving their physical, mental and moral problems.

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